

SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVING MANAGEMENT ACTIVITY

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PROGRAM FOR DETECTION OF KIDNEY DISEASES IN CHILDREN USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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ANNOTATION

In this article, as a result of the analysis of the stability of stationary solutions of the main model of helminthiasis in children, it was established that the defeat of the human body by helminthiasis leads to severe cases, and the presence of helminths in children is determined and predicted using the Pycharm Projects program.

Keywords: ostriches, crafts, artificial intelligence, forecasting, Pycharm Projects software.

INTRODUCTION

Parasites are one of the most common diseases among the population of our country and countries of the world. One of these types of parasites is the ostrich; the ostrich is a human parasite that causes enterobiasis. Medical professionals around the world are fighting this disease and providing information in scientific journals, in addition, highlighting the results of their experiments in articles and dissertations, using them in treatment and prevention. Currently, modern methods of treating this disease are being studied and confirmed in practice by the results obtained and experience. Worms are one of the oldest parasites adapted to life in the body of other

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living beings. These worms (ostriches) cause great harm to people and their health. Worms have been around since ancient times. There are currently more than 300 species of worms. According to the World Health Organization, a quarter of the world's population is infected with intestinal parasites. Several departments of medical universities are conducting research on this disease. It provides predictions using mathematical model, algorithm, use of differential equations, mathematical statistics, reliability assessment, comparison using t-Stu'dent.

Currently, the principle of a thorough study of the dynamics of roundworms is being considered, and approaches to the mathematical analysis of immunity are yielding more and more results. Today mathematical immunology is widely used. Systems analysis ideas proposed in the field of biomedicine are called “systems biology.”

In addition, medicine also uses mathematical modeling and the theory of differential equations - the largest branches of modern mathematics. The theory of differential equations is very widely used in medicine. Effective treatments for these worms can be formulated and analyzed using differential equation theory.

A mathematical model of the disease can be studied by studying the characteristics of susceptibility and reproduction of worms, the speed of spread, and the time of spread. The expert model has mainly been used to study diseases.

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Detection of worms using computer technology shows the development of modern modern technology. Let's take a look at worm predictions using Pycharm Projects' AI-powered software. Install and run the Pycharm Projects program on your computer.

```
main.py x
23 def hayuq(qiy):
24     if (qiy == "xa"):
25         return 1
26     return 0
27
28
29 2 usages
29 def probThreshold(inpProb):
30     if inpProb > 0.5:
31         return (1)
32     else:
33         return (0)
34
35
36 1 usage
36 def enter_data():
37     if (nationality_combobox1.get() == ""):
38         tkinter.messagebox.showwarning(title="Error", message="Маълумоти тўлдилинг")
39         return
40     if (nationality_combobox2.get() == ""):
41         tkinter.messagebox.showwarning(title="Error", message="Маълумоти тўлдилинг")
42         return
43     if (nationality_combobox3.get() == ""):
44         tkinter.messagebox.showwarning(title="Error", message="Маълумоти тўлдилинг")
45         return
46     if (nationality_combobox4.get() == ""):
47         tkinter.messagebox.showwarning(title="Error", message="Маълумоти тўлдилинг")
48         return
49     if (nationality_combobox5.get() == ""):
50         tkinter.messagebox.showwarning(title="Error", message="Маълумоти тўлдилинг")
51         return
hayuq() | if (qiy == "xa")
```

Figure 1. Pycharm Projects Window

The most relevant direction of using mathematical modeling in modern medicine is the description of both physiological and pathological processes.

Mathematical modeling is most effective for studying processes occurring at the level of cells, tissues, organs, and organ systems. In recent years, the possibilities of diagnosis and treatment of diseases have been greatly expanded by the introduction of mathematical modeling and the creation of computer systems based on it.

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The data is entered into the program. Disease-related parameters are recorded.

Figure 2. Artificial Intelligence Window

Figure 3. Artificial intelligence based worm detection Window.

Patient data is entered in this window. Numerical data is entered into each line and the result is obtained. Here the program detected Gigi's presence.

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Figure 4. Artificial intelligence based worm detection Window.

In the following case, patient data is also entered. A series of data is entered into each line and the result is obtained. Pycharm Projects discovered that Worm is missing.

Conclusion: Based on these data, the emergence of a number of new methods of treatment and prognosis of helminthic diseases, which occur mainly in children, allows for further assessment and conclusions. Pycharm Projects, based on artificial intelligence, is a computer technology that helps predict the appearance of worms and early detection of diseases. In medical institutions equipped with modern computer technology, the accuracy of making the correct diagnosis of a patient using this Pycharm Projects program is high, and at the same time, this program can be used as a doctor's assistant.

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